

Concept for Setting up the Overall Architecture Working Group in the NFDI Section “Common Infrastructures”

Name of the working group

Overall Architecture (OA)

Acronym

infra-oa

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Abstract

The German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) is committed to improving its research infrastructure by fostering collaboration and creating a more cohesive and interconnected system. The focus is on identifying common components, defining technical structures, and identifying requirements for cross-domain integration using agreed interfaces. The need for a common vision and architecture is emphasised in order to establish cross-domain generic services and provide an agreed framework for further developments. The Working Group "Overall Architecture" aims to develop a strategic shared vision and define an architecture for a federated research data infrastructure that supports diverse scientific communities. The group's objectives include developing a shared vision and strategy, identifying driving forces, and supporting the development of an overarching governance. The work plan includes defining guiding principles, surveying existing approaches, aligning with international activities, stakeholder management, gap analysis, and consolidating and developing a blueprint for a common infrastructure.

Motivation and Objectives

The NFDI is committed to the efficient reuse and intelligent interconnection of existing data and services through a bottom-up approach. However, the current infrastructure landscape across NFDI consortia remains diverse and loosely connected, highlighting the need for greater integration.

By leveraging existing resources and fostering collaboration, a more cohesive infrastructure can be developed to support cross-domain generic services. Achieving this requires harmonisation across user and provider communities. While services are well-tested within individual domains, they are not yet harmonised across consortia, and although common concepts regarding architectural approaches, like the Research Data Commons¹, exist, no commonly agreed understanding has been developed into this direction. A central task of the NFDI is, therefore, to identify common components, define their technical structure, and specify requirements for cross-domain integration and linkage. This task is coordinated primarily by the NFDI Section "Common Infrastructures"².

The importance of a unified vision became evident during the review of Base4NFDI service proposals, some of which were rejected due to their lack of alignment with an overarching NFDI architecture. This need for coherence was further underscored by the DFG's Key Issues Paper for the second NFDI

¹ Diepenbroek, M., Kostadinov, I., Seeger, B., Glöckner, F. O., Dieckmann, M. A., Goesmann, A., ... Sure-Vetter, Y. (2023). Towards a Research Data Commons in the German National Research Data Infrastructure NFDI: Vision, Governance, Architecture. *Proceedings of the Conference on Research Data Infrastructure*, 1. <https://doi.org/10.52825/cordi.v1i.355>

² Schimmler, S., & Diepenbroek, M. (2025). Concept of the Section "Common Infrastructures". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15000221>

funding phase³, which stresses the value of a shared architectural framework, as well as the statement by the German Alliance of Science Organisations⁴.

Nationally and internationally, the NFDI already contributes significantly to the evolution of research data management infrastructures. However, a collaboratively developed overall architecture would provide a consistent framework and guidelines for future developments, enabling more effective national and international networking and communication.

In conclusion, establishing a common architecture is essential for advancing cross-domain services and fostering coordinated development within the NFDI. It will facilitate the reuse of existing resources, support integration efforts, and guide strategic progress through a shared vision.

It is the purpose of the Working Group “Overall Architecture” to bring together the respective experts from the NFDI consortia to outline a common understanding, communication mechanisms, and the foundation for technical developments related to an overall NFDI architecture. The working group pursues the following overarching objectives:

- O1: Establish a shared vision for how a federated research data infrastructure can effectively support the diverse needs of scientific communities.
- O2: Formulate a comprehensive strategy outlining how NFDI consortia can contribute to the development and sustainability of the federated research data infrastructure.
- O3: Ensure the infrastructure is scalable, secure, and resource-efficient by leveraging existing services to build a sustainable foundation.
- O4: Identify requirements and challenges within NFDI consortia through a structured stakeholder engagement process to enhance community-wide acceptance and alignment.
- O5: Analyze and understand the unique starting points and dynamics of each NFDI consortium to identify key driving forces and foster agile development.
- O6: Facilitate the development of a transparent, adaptable, and inclusive governance model that supports long-term reliability and technological openness.

The Working Group “Overall Architecture” will therefore foster the development of the architecture for one integrated NFDI as a long-term and sustainable process within the NFDI framework. To achieve this, it will not only consider the technical and functional aspects of the NFDI architecture, but also operational as well as business-related aspects. Although these aspects are not directly within the scope of the working group, an NFDI architecture must foster the contribution, operation, federation and interoperability of scalable, in-demand services.

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<https://www.dfg.de/resource/blob/204398/dfab28aa8bb3f2864cec55fb49370e93/eckpunkte-zweite-foerderphase-en-data.pdf>

⁴ Steuerungsgremium Allianz-Schwerpunkt et al. (2024). Forschungsdatenmanagement zukunftsfest gestalten – Impulse für die Strukturevaluation der Nationalen Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14032908>

Work Plan

The work plan will be broken down into a number of activities, which will be carried out by smaller sub-groups in order to focus on specific issues. In general, one sub-group will execute one activity, but exceptions are possible. The sub-groups will report back to the working group at large, which will also oversee the various activities. While the sub-groups mentioned in this document are the first to be established, other sub-groups may be created, adapted to new needs or closed as their work is completed. All sub-groups will contribute to the objectives of the working group as defined in the previous section.

Initial Activities

Principles

This activity defines the guiding principles of the NFDI's Overall Architecture. It aims to create a set of principles that will help to ensure the scalability, security, reliability, and alignment of the services and building blocks within the NFDI Overall Architecture with the goals and strategies of the various consortia and research communities. The principles would promote consistency, facilitate collaboration, and support long-term planning for the NFDI.

Survey of Architecture Approaches within the NFDI

Several NFDI consortia have already proposed an architecture in their proposals or developed one as part of their work. In addition, Base4NFDI is funding the development of several generic services aimed at providing basic functionality within the NFDI. This activity will therefore collect existing approaches and extract commonalities that can serve as a basis for a common vision of the overall architecture and its components for the NFDI. It will also consider input from existing cloud-based and/or federated approaches already in use in the German research landscape and linked to the NFDI.

Alignment with other National and International Activities

While the approaches of many NFDI consortia are well-suited to represent their respective scientific communities, it is also necessary to take into account national and international activities in the context of the development of an overall NFDI architecture. This will help to ensure the connectivity to infrastructure projects, in particular to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC⁵), the Common European⁶ and International Data Spaces⁷ or GAIA-X⁸. Furthermore, relevant international approaches

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https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science/european-open-science-cloud-eosc_en

⁶ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-spaces>

⁷ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/>

⁸ <https://gaia-x.eu/>

like Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC⁹), NIH Research Data Commons¹⁰, or RDA Global Open Research Commons¹¹ and international community-specific approaches are considered, wherever possible. This activity will therefore review existing architectural frameworks and align them with the concepts already present within the NFDI and internationally.

Stakeholder Management & Gap Analysis

In order to analyse the gaps between the current state of development of the infrastructures in the consortia and the target architecture(s), this activity will identify relevant stakeholders and engage with them in a requirement engineering dialog. Communication and cooperation are essential for acceptance and successful implementation. All stakeholders should be kept informed of the progress, benefits and implications of the infrastructure architecture initiative. Possible methods to achieve these goals include presentations, roundtable discussions, and workshops.

Consolidation and Blueprint

Based on the results of the previous activities, common infrastructure components are consolidated and a blueprint is developed that can be reused by NFDI consortia. Such a blueprint, consisting of guiding principles and best practices, is essential for the development and operation of a common infrastructure. It has to be consistent with the NFDI goals and address issues such as standardisation, flexibility, scalability, security, and interoperability. While the guiding principles are necessary for the successful operation of the NFDI, the blueprint should clearly indicate a framework that leaves room for the specific needs of the respective communities..

Milestones

The following milestones represent the major planned outcomes of the working group. Nevertheless, further documents, statements, or papers may be released or published by the working group or members of it.

Milestone 1: Collection of Existing Architectures in NFDI Consortia published

Related activity: “Survey of Architecture Approaches within the NFDI”; Type: Document

The document “Collection of Existing Architectures in NFDI Consortia” provides a comparable description of existing architectures from NFDI consortia. “Architectures” in the document refer to the consortia’s self-conception, not to a common NFDI architectural framework.

Milestone 2: Analysis of National and International Architecture Approaches performed

Related activity: “Alignment with other National and International Activities”; Type: Document

The document provides analyses of national or international approaches, such as EOSC or GAIA-X, and places them in the context of the NFDI.

⁹ <https://ardc.edu.au/>

¹⁰ <https://commonfund.nih.gov/commons>

¹¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/global-open-research-commons-ig/activity/>

Milestone 3: NFDI Overall Architecture Framework re

Related activity: “Consolidation and Blueprint”; Type: Document

The architecture framework document describes the foundations for NFDI consortia (and other initiatives) to build an infrastructure that integrates with the overall NFDI landscape in a federated manner. It includes the guiding principles (see Activity “Principles”) as well as stakeholder requirements (see Activity “Stakeholder Management & Gap Analysis”).

Milestone 4: NFDI Overall Architecture Blueprint

Related activity: “Consolidation and Blueprint”; Type: Document

The blueprint serves as the lead technical document for NFDI consortia and other parties interested in building infrastructures to be integrated with the NFDI.

Collaboration Plan

The working group will therefore directly cooperate with different Task Areas from the existing and future NFDI consortia. Currently, the following collaboration areas have already been identified, but are subject to change:

- DataPLANT, NFDI4BIOIAMGE: Input to GA, IAM, business and operation models
- NFDI4Biodiversity: Task Area Research Data Commons
- NFDI4Cat: TA4 (Linked Extensible Infrastructure and Access Management)
- NFDI4Chem: Task Area 3 (Repositories)
- NFDI4DataScience: Task Area Infrastructure and Services
- NFDI4Earth: Task Area 3, Measure 3.1 on Architecture Synthesis
- NFDI4Immuno: Task Area Repository DevOps
- NFDI4Ing: Task Area Base Services
- NFDI-MatWerk: Task Area Materials Data Infrastructure
- NFDI4Microbiota: TA4 (Infrastructure)
- NFDI Section Infra - Working Group Multi-Cloud
- NFDI Section Infra - Working Group Research Software Engineering
- NFDI Section Infra - Working Group Identity and Access Management
- NFDI4CS: Task Area Architectures and Interfaces
- PUNCH4NFDI: TaskAreas 2 and 4 (Federated Infrastructure, Science Data Platform)
- Text+: Task Area Infrastructure/Operations

In the greater national and international context, these organisations are potential collaborators:

- Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC)
- de.NBI /ELIXIR
- Deutsches Forschungsnetzwerk (DFN)
- European Grid Initiative (EGI)
- European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)

- GAIA-X
- GÉANT
- The Software Heritage
- Verbund für Nationales Hochleistungsrechnen (NHR)

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References

References are provided in an alphabetical order:

- Common European Data Spaces: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-spaces>
- Cloud based flexible service infrastructure stack for the NFDI: 10.5281/zenodo.14392088 / <https://zenodo.org/records/14392088>
- DataPLANT Cloud Oriented Service Infrastructure: 10.52825/cordi.v1i.414, <https://www.tib-op.org/ojs/index.php/CoRDI/article/view/414/572>
- Data Mesh Architecture: <https://www.datamesh-architecture.com/>
- EOSC Federation: <https://eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation/>
- EOSC EU Node: <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/>
- EOSC Interoperability Framework: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d787ea54-6a87-11eb-aeb5-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>
- International Data Spaces Association: <https://internationaldataspaces.org/>
- NFDI4Cat - Architecture Document: <https://zenodo.org/records/10391091>
- Simpl: Cloud-to-edge federations empowering EU data spaces: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/simpl>